

Factors Influencing Diabetes Self-Management among Bhutanese People with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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ABSTRACT

Studies among Bhutanese patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) have showed alarming high rates of uncontrolled DM. However, information about diabetes self-management among this group of people is non-existent or minimal in Bhutan. The aim of the study was to examine diabetes self-management and to determine if self-efficacy, health literacy, social support and diabetes distress can predict diabetes self-management among Bhutanese patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. A total of 105 patients with T2DM visiting the diabetes clinic of Jigme Dorji Wangchuck National Referral Hospital were enrolled in the study by simple random sampling method. Six self-administered questionnaires were used to gather data including the demographic data questionnaire, the Diabetes Self-Management Questionnaire (DSMQ), the Diabetes Self-Efficacy Scale, UK version (DMSES-UK), the 3-level of Health Literacy Scale, the Chronic Illness Resource Survey (CIRS), and the Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS). Descriptive statistics and standard multiple linear regression was used to analysis the data.

The results of the study showed that participants' mean score of diabetes self-management was 7.76 (SD = 1.03) out of 10. The health care use subscale has the highest mean score of 8.73 (SD = 1.60), followed by dietary control (M = 7.76, SD = 1.03), and glucose management (M = 7.59, SD = 1.52). Physical activity subscale (M = 7.02, SD = 2.18) had the lowest mean score among the subscales. Results of the standard multiple linear regression analysis indicated that self-efficacy, health literacy, social support and diabetes

distress explained 17.16% in the variance of diabetes self-management among Bhutanese patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. However, only self-efficacy could significantly predict diabetes self-management ($\beta = .277, p = .015$).

The findings provide an evidence for health care providers to develop the interventional program aimed at improving self-efficacy to promote diabetes self-management activities such as glucose management, physical activity and dietary control in Bhutanese patients with T2DM

Keywords: [Type 2 Diabetes mellitus, Diabetes self-management, Health literacy, Self-efficacy, Social support, Diabetes distress]

INTRODUCTION

The International Diabetes Federation [IDF] in 2019 estimated that approximately 463 million people are living with diabetes in 2019 and it was expected to rise to 700 million in 2045, out of which 153 million people affected will be in South East Asia. Bhutan had seen decrease in the incidence of T2DM in last few years(1). However, the prevalence rate of T2DM in Bhutan is estimated to be 10.3%, where 1 in every 12 adults is living with T2DM, which is relatively high compared other country such as Bangladesh (2). It is estimated that 1.6 million people died due to diabetes in 2016 alone (3) and diabetes caused death of 4.2 million people in 2019 (2). The health care cost due to diabetes is also on the rise and the IDF (2019) shows that at least 760 million USD dollars is spent on managing

diabetes around the world. Diabetic-related complications such as microvascular and macro vascular complications contribute to increased morbidity, mortality, health care cost and reduced quality of life of the patients with T2DM. It increases economic burden of diabetes mellitus, because the increase in complications increases the total health cost (4).

The goal of diabetes care is to maintain HbA1c of 7% and lower. Diabetes self-management (DSM) is the cornerstone of diabetes care, as diabetes care becomes more patient centred and community-based care (5). Proper diabetes self-management (DSM) can prevent harmful and costly microvascular and macro-vascular complications. Several studies show that effective DSM can help reduce and achieve optimal HbA1c level (6-8). Studies among Bhutanese people with T2DM has showed that optimal glycaemic control was not achieved in 46% to 72% of the participants (9-11), which might reflect poor DSM among these group of people.

DSM refers to activities people with T2DM perform every day to help control blood sugar level and prevent complications. It includes glucose level monitoring and management by adhering to diabetes medications, healthy diet, and regular physical activities. Bhutanese diabetics are found to have low to moderate level of adherence to medication (10), moderate level of healthy eating behaviour (12) and moderate level of physical activity (9).

Several previous studies show that many factors have influence on DSM (13-16). The individual and family self-management theory (IFSMT) of Ryan and Sawin (2009) also suggest that several factors might have influence on DSM. Based on the literature reviews and IFSMT, the effect of four factors- health literacy, self-efficacy, diabetes distress and social support on DSM was examined in this study.

Health literacy is the ability of the person to collect and analyse health

information to make decisions related to health and wellbeing on addition to the basic ability to read and write (17). Patients with low health literacy have limited knowledge and information about their health which will in turn limit them to self-manage and make decision about their health (17). Low health literacy was associated with lower level of knowledge and low management among patients with T2DM (18). Studies show that health literacy was positively associated with DSM (19, 20) and could predict DSM significantly (16).

Self-efficacy in DSM is the confidence in the skills and ability of people with T2DM to undertake the activities that is required to maintain sustained glycaemic control and prevent complications. People with high self-efficacy feel they are competent to perform a task and complete it successfully (21). Many studies have established that high self-efficacy is associated with high DSM and that it can predict DSM significantly (13-15, 22, 23). Self-efficacy influences either the components of DSM or the total DSM.

The management of diabetes is also related to emotional factors. Diabetes distress is described as range of psychological responses which arises when a person with T2DM experience burden and worries specific to experience of living with T2DM and managing it (5). Diabetes distress lowers self-efficacy and lowers the patient's perception of ability to control diabetes (5, 24). Studies have shown that higher diabetes distress is barrier to effective DSM (25) and can lower the DSM among T2DM patients (26, 27).

Social support is the assistance provided by friends and family in times of need (28). Social support helps in improving knowledge, increasing self-regulations and self-efficacy skills (29), thus leading to improved DSM. Social support can improve self-management by reducing the impact of stress, increasing self-efficacy and bringing change in the negative health behaviours of the patients with T2DM (30).

Studies have established that social support is positively related and can significantly predict DSM (13, 14).

Many studies investigating these factors have been carried out in different places and setting but the results of the studies were inconsistent, thus reducing the possibility of generalization. Moreover, no study on DSM and its influencing factors have been carried out in Bhutan till now. The different traditions and culture practiced in Bhutan might have influence on the DSM and factors influencing DSM among Bhutanese diabetics, thus making it distinct from studies done in other countries. The objectives of the study were to explore DSM and examine factors influencing DSM among Bhutanese people with T2DM. We hypothesized that self-efficacy, health literacy, social support and diabetes distress can predict DSM among adult Bhutanese people with type 2 DM

MATERIALS & METHODS

1. Design, setting, and sample

A predictive correlational study was used for this study. Participants were Bhutanese T2DM who came to the diabetes OPD of Jigme Dorji Wangchuck National Referral Hospital (JDWRH), Thimphu Bhutan, for their regular follow-up. A simple random sampling method was used to recruit 105 participants who met the following inclusion criteria: 1) aged 18-60 years old, 2) have diagnosed with T2DM for at least 6 months, 3) are able to read and write in English, 4) have good orientation and no history of mental illness, and 5) have no major physical disability.

2. Data collection

Participants were taken to a private room and a set of six questionnaires were distributed to collect data. Written informed consent were taken from the participants. Each participant was able to complete the self-reported questionnaires in average time of 40 minutes.

2.1 Demographic data of the participants

The general characteristics and health information of the participants were collected using the demographic data questionnaire developed by the researcher specifically for this study. Some data were self-reported by the participants, while some data were collected from the medical record book of the participants.

2.2. Diabetes self-management

DSM was measured by using the Diabetes Self-management Questionnaire (31), which consists of 16 items used in assessing self-care activities in four subscales (glucose management, dietary control, physical activities and health-care use). Each item is scored on a 4-point Likert scale. Nine negatively worded items (items 5, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16) needs to be reversed scored. The final raw score is converted to score ranging from 0 to 10. Higher score shows optimal diabetes self-management. The Cronbach's alpha was .66 for this study.

2.3 Health literacy

The health literacy of the participants for this study was measured using The Functional, Communicative and Critical health literacy scale (32). The scale is made up of 14 items which can be divided into 3 subscales. Each item is scored on a 4-point Likert like scale, and final score is given as either mean of each subscale or of all 14 items ranging from 1 to 4. Higher score indicates higher health literacy level. The Cronbach's alpha was .89 for this study.

2.4 Self-efficacy

The Diabetes Management Self-Efficacy Scale - UK version (DMSES-UK) was used to measure the self-efficacy among the participants (33). It is made up of 15 items, where each items are scored between 0-10, with a possible score range of 0 to 150. Self-efficacy can be divided into low (score 0-50), moderate (score 51-100) and high self-efficacy (101-150). The Cronbach's alpha was .82 for this study.

2.5 Diabetes distress

Diabetes distress was measured using the Diabetes distress scale, which consists of 17

items and can be divided into four subscale (34). Each of the item is scored in a 6-point Likert type scale and is scored as a mean of each subscale or total items. The possible score range is from 1 to 6. A score of 2 or less shows no or little distress, score of 2 to 2.9 shows moderate diabetes distress and score of 3 or more shows high diabetes distress (35). The Cronbach's alpha was .68 for this study.

2.6 Social support

Social support was measured by the two subscale 'Family and friends' and 'doctor and health care team' of the Chronic Illness Resource Survey (CIRS) (36). The subscales are made up of 8 items and 7 items respectively, and each item is scored on a 5-point Likert-type scale. The possible score range for the 2 subscales combined was 15 to 17. Higher score indicates higher social support (13). The Cronbach's alpha was .73 for this study.

3. Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Burapha University, Thailand (IRB number: G-Hs 005/2563) and Research Ethical board of Ministry of Health (REBH), Bhutan (REBH/Approval/2020/001).

Statistical Analysis

The influence of health literacy, self-efficacy, diabetes distress and social support was tested by performing standard multiple linear regression at significant level of .05.

All assumptions of MLR were tested and met. Demographic data of the participants were analysed using descriptive statistics. All statistical analysis was performed using Minitab17 software.

RESULTS

1. Characteristics and health information of the participants

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics and health information of the participants, which includes gender, age, income, diabetes duration, diabetic medication, HbA1c level and the presence of comorbidities and diabetes-related complications. A total of 105 participants were recruited for this study, which consisted of 47 males and 58 females. The mean age of the participants was 49.6 years, with majority of participants in age group of 41 to 60 years old. Majority of the participants (54.3%) earned income in the range of Nu. 10000- 30,000 (1 Nu = 0.013US\$), which is considered above the poverty line in Bhutan (37). The mean diabetes duration is 74.7 months (approximately 6 years). Majority of the participants were on oral diabetic medications. 60.9% of the participants had only one type of co-morbidity. 20.9% of the participants have developed one or more complications related to diabetes. Interestingly, 75.2% of the participants were either overweight or obese, while 36.2% had HbA1c more than 7%, and 61.9% of the participants had HbA1c less than 7%,

Table 1 Demographic data and health characteristics of participants (N = 105)

Characteristics	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	47	44.8
Female	58	55.2
Age (<i>M</i> = 49.6, <i>SD</i> = 8.06, <i>Min</i> = 29, <i>max</i> = 60)		
18-30 years	2	1.9
31-40 years	14	13.3
41-50 years	32	30.5
51-60 years	57	54.3
Monthly family income (1 Nu = 0.013 USD) (n=102)		
< Nu 5000	11	10.8
Nu 5000-10000	11	10.8
Nu 10,000-30,000	57	55.9
Nu >30,00	23	22.5
Adequacy of family income (n = 103)		
Adequate	94	91.3
Inadequate	9	8.7

Diagnosis duration ($M = 74.72$, $SD = 75.75$, $Min = 6$, $Max = 348$ [29 years])		
< 1 year (< 12 months)	9	8.6
1-5 years (12- 60 months)	58	55.2
6 – 10 years (61 -120 months)	12	11.4
>10 years (> 120 months)	26	24.8
Diabetic Medication		
Oral medications	96	91.5
Insulin	3	2.8
Combined therapy	4	3.8
None	2	1.9
Comorbidities		
None	34	32.4
1 comorbidity	64	60.9
Hypertension	58	90.6
Others (Heart diseases, Arthritis, Gout)	6	9.4
>1 comorbidities	7	6.7
Diabetic related complications		
None	83	79.1
Retinopathy	5	4.8
Neuropathy	11	10.5
Nephropathy	3	2.8
>1 complications	3	2.8
BMI ($M = 27.9$, $SD = 4.6$, $Min = 20.4$, $max = 49.6$)		
Normal weight (18.5 – 24.9)	26	24.8
Overweight (25-29.9)	54	51.4
Obese (> 30)	25	23.8
Glycemic control (HbA1c level) ($M = 7.21$, $SD = 2.16$, $Min = 4.3$, $Max = 16.3$) (n = 103)		
Controlled T2DM (HbA1c \leq 7%)	65	63.1
Uncontrolled T2DM (HbA1c > 7%)	38	36.9
Moderately uncontrolled (7.1 - 8%)	19	50
Highly uncontrolled (> 8)	19	50

2. Diabetes self-management (DSM)

DSM was divided into four subscales. The mean score of DSM was 7.76 (SD = 1.03), out of 10. The mean score for subscale glucose management (GM), dietary control (DC), physical activity (PA) and healthcare use (HCU) were 7.59, 7.61, 7.02 and 8.73 respectively. It was found that the HCU had the highest mean score followed by DC subscale, then GM subscale and physical activity subscale had the lowest mean score. Table 2 shows the details of DSM among the participants in this study.

Table 2 Mean and standard deviation of Diabetes self-management and its subscales

DV and subscales	Possible score	Actual score	M	SD
Diabetes self-management	0 – 10	5.4 – 9.8	7.76	1.03
Glucose management	0 – 10	3.3 – 10	7.59	1.52
Dietary control	0 – 10	1.7 – 10	7.61	1.45
Physical activity	0 – 10	1.1 – 10	7.02	2.18
Health care use	0 – 10	3.3 - 10	8.73	1.60

3. Scores of independent variables

Table 3 shows the details of independent variables. The health literacy score ranged from 1.3 to 4, with mean of 2.61 (SD = .65). The self-efficacy level of the participants ranged from 70 – 143, with mean score of 106.9 (SD = 15.73) which indicated high level of self-efficacy. The overall score of diabetes distress (DDS) ranged from 1 to 2, which indicated no or little distress, with a mean of 1.40 (SD = 0.23). The social support score ranged from 43 to 72 with a mean of 58.99 (SD = 5.90).

Table 3 Scores of independent variables

Independent Variables	Possible score	Actual score	M	SD	Level
Health literacy	1 – 4	1.3 – 4	2.61	0.65	-
Self-efficacy	0 - 150	70 - 143	106.9	15.73	High
Diabetes distress	1 – 6	1 – 2	1.40	0.23	No or little DDS
Social support	15 – 75	43 – 72	58.99	5.90	-

4. Factors influencing DSM among Bhutanese patients with T2DM

Self-efficacy, social support and diabetes distress were associated with DSM significantly, while health literacy was not associated significantly with DSM as shown in

table 4. The standard multiple regression analysis showed all the variables can explain 17.16% variance in DSM. It showed that self-efficacy could predict DSM among the Bhutanese people with T2DM significantly, while health literacy, social support and diabetes could not predict DSM significantly. The details of the results from MLR are presented in table 5.

Table 4 Correlation matrix among the variables (n = 105)

	Diabetes self-management	Self-efficacy	Health literacy	Social support	Diabetes distress
Diabetes self-management	1.000				
Self-efficacy	0.365***	1.000			
Health Literacy	0.059	0.428***	1.000		
Social Support	0.351***	0.525***	0.326***	1.000	
Diabetes Distress	-0.300**	-0.314***	-0.094	-0.416***	1.000

*** p < .001 ** p < .01

Table 5 Regression analysis for variables predicting DSM (n = 105)

Predicting variables	B	SE	B	T	p-value
Self-efficacy	.018	.007	.277	2.48	.015
Health literacy	-.214	.158	-.135	-1.35	.181
Social support	.033	.019	.188	1.68	.096
Diabetes distress	-.653	.439	-.148	-1.49	.140
Constant = 5.34, Adj R ² = 17.16 %, F _(4, 100) = 6.39, p < .001					

DISCUSSION

The study explored DSM and examined the factors influencing DSM among Bhutanese people with T2DM.

1. DSM among Bhutanese people with T2DM

Assessment of DSM was based on four activities performed by participants, which included glucose management, dietary control, physical activity and health care use. The mean score of total DSM among participants for this study was 7.76 out the possible score of 10. The mean score of health care use (HCU) was the highest score ($M = 8.73$, $SD = 1.60$), followed by dietary control (DC) ($M = 7.76$, $SD = 1.03$), and glucose management (GM) ($M = 7.59$, $SD = 1.52$). The mean score of physical activity (PA) was the lowest score ($M = 7.02$, $SD = 2.18$). The overall mean score and mean scores of subscale of DSM were higher than 7 (out of 10), which indicate that adult Bhutanese patients with type 2 DM had relatively higher diabetes self-management. A similar study in Iran showed that the mean score of DSM, GM, DC, HCU and PA were 6.92, 6.25, 7.48, 7.23 and 7.05 respectively (38). A study in Thailand showed had participants scored the

highest in HCU subscale (39), which was similar to result of current study. The result of current study is similar to a study done in Australia which showed that DSM was higher among the participants(40).

This result can be explained by the characteristics of the participants in the study as suggested by the IFMST(29). The IFMST by Ryan and Sawin (2009) suggests that individual and family characteristics, severity and complexity of disease conditions, social and environmental factors such as access to health care, income or tradition have influence on how the individual and family manage care for T2DM. Evidently, majority of the participants were middle age adults, who were physically fit and mentally sound to carry out diabetes self-management activities effectively, which are difficult for younger or older people. Younger adults are noncompliant to treatment regimens (41, 42), while older adults are physically limited or cognitively impaired, which is associated with poorer capacity to self-manage diabetes (43, 44). Most of the participants were married and lived with family and friends, therefore receiving good social support in performing DSM and managing their diabetes (14, 29, 45). Moreover, The government of Bhutan provides universal health coverage to all the people in the country (46), which includes diabetes care services for all people with T2DM. This has help reduce financial burden of individuals with T2DM and their families. Additionally, most of the

participants of the study claimed to have adequate monthly income. Financial stability could help maintain higher DSM (47). In addition, the presence of fewer comorbidities and diabetes-related complications can result in better and effective DSM (29, 48, 49), as seen in this study. Majority of participants in this study have been living with T2DM for 1 to 5 year. They had the time to understand the disease and enough time to learn and practice self-management behaviors to respond to it positively (50)

Though the mean score of DSM was closer to optimal score, the study result showed that large percentage of the participants were either *overweight or obese* and some of the participants were not able to control their blood sugar level. Relatively lower physical activity seen among the participants might have contributed to suboptimal weight control and glucose level control. Interventions aiming to educate the participants about these concerns and improving the level of physical activity among the participants might be successful in attaining optimal glucose management.

2. Factors influencing DSM among Bhutanese people with T2DM

Self-efficacy was found to predict DSM study significantly among the participants in this study. Many previous studies have supported this finding and showed that self-efficacy is a strong predictor of DSM among people with T2DM (15, 16, 22, 23, 51). People with T2DM need to learn skills and set up habits of eating healthy food, doing regular physical exercise, adhering to diabetes medication and carrying out regular follow up with the health care centers. The IFSMT suggest that individuals and families develop self-efficacy when they start gaining knowledge and belief about certain self-care activity, which in-turn will help improve self-management (29). Self-confidence in one's capability to carry out these activities can help change one's health care behaviour by self-initiating self-care

activities, thus, bringing a positive influence on diabetes self-management (21). Self-efficacy among the participants in this study was reported to be high, thus resulting in mean score of total DSM to be closer to the optimal score.

Diabetes distress was negatively and significantly associated with DSM among the participants in this study which was similar to a previous study (26) but diabetes distress could not able to predict DSM significantly. The IFSMT of Ryan and Sawin (2009) show that control of emotions is necessary to effectively self-manage diabetes. Diabetes distress lowers adherence to self-management activities and lowers self-efficacy, thus resulting in poor DSM (5, 24). Bhutanese people are traditional and mainly live together as a big family, who support each other in times of need. Additionally, most of Bhutanese are religious (dominantly Buddhist) and believe in law of 'Karma' (52). They believe that it is their 'bad karma' that have resulted in having to live with T2DM, thus they accept the disease as normal part of their life. Good social support from family members and their religious belief might act as a buffer in reducing the impact of diabetes distress on DSM. Therefore, diabetes distress had low association with DSM and it could not predict DSM significantly in this study.

Social support was associated with DSM positively and significantly in this study but it could not predict DSM significantly as suggested in previous studies (13, 14, 53). Social support can help improve knowledge and self-efficacy, thus resulting in better DSM among people with T2DM (29). In this study, social support from only two sources – family and health care professional were assessed, while it was possible that the participants might have receive support from other source as well. Inconsistency and imbalance in the support received from these two sources was also report by the participants, which might have caused some participants to perceive relatively low social support. Additionally, majority of the participants

were healthy middle aged adults, who were capable of caring for themselves, thus not requiring support to perform activities related to themselves. These reasons might have resulted in weaker association among the variables, thus social support could not predict DSM significantly.

Another study finding revealed that there was no association between health literacy and DSM, which contradicted many previous studies (16, 19, 20, 54). High level of health literacy can improve DSM by increasing knowledge, and it was lack of knowledge that predicted low self-management (40). In this study, the actual knowledge of participants was not measured. Moreover, most of the participants lived with their family, thus health literacy of the family could also have affected the DSM among the participants, which was not assessed in this study.

This study shows that self-efficacy is the only factor that could predict DSM significantly, among Bhutanese population with T2DM.

CONCLUSION

The study findings highlight that adults Bhutanese with T2DM had high DSM, with the highest mean score in the healthcare use subscale, followed by dietary control, glucose management, and the lowest score in the physical activity subscale. The result also revealed that majority of the participants have problems in controlling their body weight and some of the participants were not able to control their glucose level. This study showed that self-efficacy could predict diabetes self-management significantly, while health literacy, social support and diabetes distress could not predict diabetes self-management significantly, among people with T2DM in Bhutan. However, the results showed that the variables interacted with each other, thus directly or indirectly helping improve self-efficacy. Ryan and Sawin (2009) in their IFSMT suggests that all that these factors might have influence on one another, thus

ultimately influencing diabetes self-management.

The findings provide an evidence for health care providers to develop the interventional programs aimed at improving self-efficacy to promote diabetes self-management activities in Bhutanese people with T2DM. Programs aimed at increasing the self-efficacy of T2DM patients may help the Bhutanese people with T2DM improve and maintain high level of diabetes self-management in many years to come.

Future research should focus on studying other variables such as diabetes knowledge and physical and social environment, which might have influence on DSM as suggested by results of this study and the IFSMT by Ryan and Sawin (2009). Similar study should be carried out in other hospitals in Bhutan and instruments to study these variables should be adapted to fit the Bhutanese population accurately. Experimental study using the results of this study could also be planned in the future.

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